

RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART I. STUDY OF THE ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF THE CHLORO DERIVATIVES OF THE SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID.

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In the present study it is expected to throw some light on the relationship between the chemical activity of the chloro derivatives of the various substituted amides of malonic acid of the type: $\text{Cl}_2 : \text{C} : (\text{CONHR})_2$, $\text{Cl}_2 : \text{C} : (\text{CONH}_2)(\text{CONHR})$ and $(\text{Cl})(\text{ClCH}_2) : \text{C} : (\text{CONHR})_2$, where R is phenyl, tolyl, etc.

The results of absorption spectra of the above compounds have been compared with the absorption spectra measurements of the compounds of the type $\text{H}_2 : \text{C} : (\text{CONHR})_2$ studied by Ramart, Naik and Trivedi (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1934, 1, 525).

The comparison of these two corresponding sets of curves shows that the transformation of methylene group CH_2 into CCl_2 group produces a distinct change in the nature of the curves.

In 1913 Victor Henri proposed a law stating that 'Along with several other effects, substances of which the molecules are reactive, also show a strong exaltation in their power of absorbing ultraviolet rays.' (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, 185, 1997).

More recently one of us (Ramart, *Compt. rend.*, 1932 195, 7216) announced that, as long as the internal condition of a chromophore remains the same, the chemical activity of this chromophore with regard to another molecule (with which it may enter into reaction) remains unaltered. Numerous examples of this excellent relationship between the chemical activity and the absorption in the ultraviolet of organic molecules exist in literature.

Herein are embodied the investigations with regard to the relationship between the chemical activity of the chloro derivatives of the various substituted amides of malonic acid of the types :

and their absorption in the ultraviolet. The following substances were obtained in optically pure condition for spectrographic examination.

(1) Dichloromalon-di-phenylamide, (2) dichloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (3) dichloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (4) dichloromalon-di-*m*-(chloro)-tolylamide, (5) dichloromalon-di-1:3:4-xylylide, (6) dichloromalon-di-heptylamide, (7) dichloromalon-dibenzylamide, (8) dichloromalon-mono-*p*-tolylamide, (9) dichloromalon-mono (chloro)-phenylamide, (10) chloromethyl-chloromalon-diphenylamide, (11) chloromethyl-chloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (12) chloromethyl-chloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide.

The relationship which exists between the chemical activity of the simple amides of malonic acid and their absorption in the ultraviolet has been already studied (*cf.* Ramart, Naik and Trivedi, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1934, 1, 525).

FIG. 1.

800 900 1000 1100 1200 1300
3750 3333 3000 2750 2500 2307

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to dichloromalon diphenylamide, - and -di-*o*-, *p*- and *m*-tolylamides,

FIG. 2.

1000 1100 1200 1300 1400
3000 2730 2500 2307 2142

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to malon-diphenylamide and -di-*o*-, *m*- and *p*-tollylamides.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The examination was made by means of the Chemists' spectrograph of Zeiss. The source of ultraviolet rays was Chalmers hydrogen lamp. It was supplied by the electric current from a 2,000 volt sector (transformed from 110 volts). The solvent and the solution of the substance to be studied were placed in two similar tubes with end quartz plates. The tube containing the solvent is preceded by sector photometer which reduces the flux of light by means of an adjustable angle of overture. The system of two tubes is followed by a Hüller prism which brings the two juxtaposed spectra on the sensitised photographic plates. The pairs of spectra thus produced can be photographed between wave-length scales marked in ordinary Angstrom wave-length units.

FIG. 3.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to dichloro-malon-monochlorophenylamide, diheptylamide and, dibenzylamide.

FIG. 4.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to chloro-malon-diphenylamide, di-*o*, di-*p*-tolylamide and malon-di-*p*-tolylamide.

The results of spectrographic examinations are represented by marking the position of the absorption bands (as shown with reference to the wavelength scale) along the abscissae, and the corresponding molecular extinctions are marked along ordinates.

The molecular extinction is obtained from the following formula:—

$$E = \frac{1}{cd} \log_{10} \frac{I_0}{I}$$

where, I_0 is the intensity of the incident ray; I , the intensity of the emerging ray; E , the coefficient of molecular extinction, and c , the molecular concentration of the solution under experiment; d , the length of the column of the solution through which the ray is passing.

The above formula could also be expressed as

$$E = \frac{1}{cd} \log_{10} \frac{2\pi}{\alpha}$$

where, α is the angle of the sector, through which the light is passing. Sometimes instead of the coefficient of the molecular extinction itself, its logarithm is plotted along the ordinates. The curves given in Fig. 1 represent the results of our observations, which can be summarised as follows :

1. The general nature and sense of the corresponding curves of the simple malonamides and the chloro derivatives are similar (*cf.* Figs. 1 and 2).
2. The effect of the transformation of CH_2 into CCl_2 group, is to bring about enhanced general absorption. This results in the shifting of curves towards the visible region. Again, the secondary band due to the methylene group disappears in the curves of the chloro derivatives. (*cf.* the curves of malon-diphenylamide and dichloromalon-diphenylamide in Figs. 2 and 1 respectively).
3. The nature of the radicals attached to the carbonyl groups determines the position and nature of the curves of absorption. This is illustrated by the curves of dichloromalon-diphenylamide and dichloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide (Fig. 1).
4. The molecular weight of the radicals attached to the imino grouping determines the extent of absorption. The heavier the radicals, the greater shifting of the curve of absorption towards the visible (*cf.* Figs. 1 and 3, as also 1 and 5).
5. When the radicals have the same number of carbon atoms, absorption is determined by the constitution of such radicals. Open-chain radicals give simple curves; whereas ring structures give many banded curves,

FIG. 5.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to malon-mono-phenylamide, *o*-tolylamide, malon-diheptylamide and malonamide

This is illustrated by the cases of dichloromalon-diheptylamide and dichloromalon-dibenzylamide. (curves 2 and 3 in Fig. 2.)

6. In the case of the three tolylamide derivatives, the position of the absorption curves is affected by the proximity or distance of the methyl group to or from the amino grouping (Fig. 1.)

7. In the case of the derivatives $\begin{matrix} \text{ClCH}_2 \\ \text{Cl} \end{matrix} \text{C} \begin{matrix} \text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{R} \\ \text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{R} \end{matrix}$ the secondary band due to the methylene group situated between the two carbonyl groups has disappeared. This is due to the fact that the CH_2 group has been converted into

